

INCREASE IN STARTUPS BY HAVING HYBRID METHOD OF ONLINE AND OFFLINE LECTURES FOR GRADUATION AND MASTERS STUDENTS

Priyanka Sobaran Singh

Bharat College of Arts and Commerce, Badlapur (w)

Abstract:

Online education has got a boon due to covid-19 pandemic, where moving outside was not possible. We know about many online education institutes which provide online modes of teaching with the best services and output. Our traditional method of teaching in India is about to change the new Education Policy approved by the Union Cabinet of India on 29 July 2020, replaces the previous National Policy on Education, 1986. Just like this policy we can also add an hybrid mode of teaching with 4 days of online mode and 2 days for offline lectures for graduation and masters pursuing students, which will include practical as well. By implementing it students will find more time to build their career, they will save their time to start with an entrepreneurship. Travelling time will be saved by students doing their graduation and masters. As an online degree approved by the Distance Education Council of India, is also accepted by many companies, so this change in education will not affect the students' concern related to jobs. Problems related to network issues for online education will remain a factor of concern but it could definitely be minimized. Startups, entrepreneurship are started by new, innovative ideas which are commonly found in college going students. In India millions startups were started by peoples in the field of their interest. Covid-19 has provided us with this platform where we have tried to build up a layer accepting the digital platform, go local for vocal has increased which have provided a good input in gross domestic production growth rate. Moving to combination of online and offline mode will also reduce the problem of salary concern in some places paid to teachers. This implementation will give also give teachers a platform to work from home and in building their career. Proper management and etiquette will be the key concern will adapting it.

Keywords: *online, education, offline, lectures, entrepreneurs*

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Introduction

Indian education has got a drastic challenge in pandemic situations dealing with problems of network reach, gadget inefficiency and availability in many places. Overcoming many such problems still we manage to provide education. Online communication has made us to interact with different peoples staying very far away. We have connected with peoples from all parts of country even with world in this pandemic situation by communicating in online mode. The Distance Education Council in India was established in 1991 under IGNOU (Indira Gandhi National Open University) Act, 1985 was responsible for promotion and coordination of Open and Distance Learning. Almost many countries from different continents are providing online mode for education for graduation and masters students. It is easy for them as they have the internet and gadgets available very efficiently. Despite India being the second largest online market in the world, only 50% of internet access is there. About 32% of active internet users are from rural areas and 67% from urban areas. These number are increasing as government is focusing on Digital India and even my companies like Google was providing India with many project like Google Internet Balloon i.e. Loon in many rural areas to provide internet access.

LIS (Library and Information Science) was started in India in 1985 providing distance and open learning mode courses by B.R.Ambedkar Open University and followed by the Bachelor's degree programme started by the Indira Gandhi National Open University. There are many platforms which provide degrees for online education either by taking live sessions or by uploading pre-recorded videos, outcome of such companies are up to the mark. This gives us the idea that online mode will perform better if adopted. IBM have found that participants learn five times more material in online learning courses using multimedia content compared with traditional face to face courses. They are able to move faster through areas of the course they feel comfortable with, but slower through those that they need a little more time on.

Byju's, a multinational education company of India, will have around 6 million students enrolled by 2020. Dexler Education, Educomp Solutions, IGNOU, Edukart, Simplilearn, Meritnation, Excelsoft are some of the top online education companies in India in 2021. Online education provides synchronous as well asynchronous mode between students and

teachers, thus providing a more flexible environment. SpaceX satellite broadband arm Starlink is also aiming to start broadband services in India from December 2022. All such steps by many companies will reduce our network reach issue to remote areas. Only connectivity or gadget inefficiency is not the only problem, teachers were not getting handy on machines. Lokesh Talikatte, State unit president, Recognised Unaided Private Schools' Association, Karnataka, said that nearly 80% of higher primary and high school have stopped online classes as teachers are unable to manage the workload. Problem of gadget knowledge could be removed entirely by providing proper training to teachers.

In India startups have increased by 1 million in the last year. Students have started many new startups by putting their likes or hobbies in it. Here are a few successful startups founded by college students: Facebook, Yahoo, FedEx, Snapchat, Time Magazine and many more. College students come with maximum new ideas as they are involved with the current world and studying about it. Students continuously gain knowledge which helps them in connecting many topics and builds a new inherited topic from it.

Many initiatives have been taken place by schools, colleges, even by private institutes for building entrepreneurship in students, even countries are providing an initiative to students for educating them in entrepreneurship. Country growth rate is measured with change in nation's gross domestic product, foreign trade, and many more factors. Startups, entrepreneurship will increase our country's growth rate rapidly and will give a platform in the long run. Students going to colleges has great and innovative ideas as they are in learning and connecting phase.

By having 4 days online lectures and 2 days offline lectures problem concern with teachers related to acceptance of devices, working on platform used for online mode teaching will also be accepted by teachers. Teachers will come to know how to use technology. Teachers/ professors from many states from India do have concern about their less salary. This salary problem will also be reduced as teachers will be also work from home for online lectures of students, for approx. 3-4 days. Teachers can now focus on their area of interest, thus increasing their source of income.

Need of change in offline mode of education:

World has moved from physical classrooms to virtual classrooms, this pandemic has shown us the issue for virtual classrooms, hence we are now partly ready to move to virtual classrooms. In India by the age of 21 students get a degree, by 23 they complete their masters, they get very less to think over their likes or starting a new business.

Shifting education partially to online will provide them more time to think about careers and even if they can start their own business, they can become entrepreneurs. Yes it is true that the physical mode of practical will have a different output so 4 days online and 2 days offline lectures will provide enhancement in students career.

Some students work because of financial issues as they don't have any other option instead of working, some students travel for hours just to reach college premises, all these problems will be solved up to a mark. Travelling time will be reduced by students thus providing a time for building a career.

By moving to online platforms, issues related to teachers/ professors' concern with their salaries will also be solved. Teachers will also work 3-4 days from home thus building their own career. Quality of education will remain the first priority even by accepting it. Quality of education will be maintained by solving the doubts of students in offline mode and having offline exam as usual.

Objective:

To provide more startups and entrepreneurship as students will have self-time after attaining online lectures.

Research Methodology:

Data was collected with the help of Google form. Google form collects the data which is used for analyzing our survey. Google form is a free software for survey administration offered by Google. Covid-19 pandemic has shown a side where visiting our dear ones should be avoided, in such a situation taking a survey was impossible. Google form helps in online data collection.

Findings:

Survey was conducted on students who are in and who have completed their graduation and masters. Sample space of 27 was collected from various part of countries ranging from students completed or pursuing their graduation or masters were no barrier for age group was taken. According to a survey, students' experience is not having a positive feedback related to online lectures, still some were satisfied with online lectures as visual representation for some topics were shown to them. By visual representation students have got a clear overview of actual system working and their inter connection. Covid-19 has given us a platform where education was possible in a different way with such problem but successful in overall performance. Students have saved time in this pandemic from travelling which was used by students in building their own likes. Around 35% of

students liked online lectures rest had issues related to connection, disturbance, not getting topics cleared because of lack of voice from teachers end.

Students have faced many issues while attaining online lectures like network issues, background disturbance, social media platform, less interactive. Students are also lacking the disciplines that used to be in offline lectures also facing the issues of communication barrier which was reduced in offline lectures. This online platform has affected those students most who had phobia in communicating with others as they have remained isolated. Offline lectures provide good communication skills, confidence. This confidence in students for communication will also be a major issue but could be controlled as offline activities, lectures and some session will be continued.

Students are ok with the hybrid mechanism of having 4 days online lectures and 2 days offline lectures, offline lectures specially for practical. 65.2% students said yes for 4 days offline lectures and 2 days online lectures with a point that online should be conducted properly within specified college time.

Will it be ok according to you to have 3 or 4 days online lecture and 2 or 3 days offline lectur specially for practical?
23 responses

13% students thinks that online lectures will provide with a new startups and entrepreneurships in Indian market, majority that is 47.8% are not cleared with it, they are in confusion.

Suggestions:

Moving from offline to online should be in such a way that attitudes of students are properly maintained while being in lecture, entering and leaving of lectures should be administered properly. Within lecture hours it should be strictly followed that no consumption of food, beverages or any other activities be done within that specified time which will lead to distraction. Students can do their work but not cross their attitudes or limits. In case of travelling or any work which could not be avoided students should mail it prior. Social media use should be strictly avoided while attending virtual classes.

Conclusion:

Indians are not currently ready to adopt online classes. Once network connectivity and all other distractions come under control, hybrid type education will take a next level in career building of students from their college days itself. This step in long run will provide a great future to the Indian market for increasing the countries growth rate.

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